

Traumatic Brain Injury and its Link to Alzheimer's Disease

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Abstract

The intricate relationship between traumatic brain injury (TBI) and Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a focal point of neuroscientific inquiry. Growing evidence suggests that individuals with a history of TBI may face an elevated risk of developing memory loss later in life, including a persistent pattern connecting moderate and severe TBI with an elevated vulnerability to Alzheimer's disease and related dementias. This revelation raises significant public health concerns, prompting an in-depth exploration with a focus shift to the intricate interplay between TBI and alterations in both brain structure and function.

Of particular interest are the roles played by beta amyloid (A β) and tau protein, two molecular protagonists implicated in the trajectory from TBI to Alzheimer's pathology. Unravelling these intricacies not only elucidates the link between TBI and neurodegenerative disorders but also illuminates potential avenues for preventive interventions against Alzheimer's disease. This article contributes to a nuanced understanding of the profound consequences of TBI, offering insights that inform public health initiatives and clinical strategies.

Keywords: Traumatic Brain Injury (TBI), Alzheimer's Disease, Beta amyloid (A β), Tau, Oxidative Stress, Inflammation

Introduction

Traumatic brain injuries (TBIs) have become a prominent public health concern, impacting millions annually. The Centre for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) has provided an annual estimate, indicating that around 1.5 million Americans endure a traumatic brain injury (TBI). Among this population, approximately 230,000 individuals require hospitalization. Notably, the number of

diagnosed TBIs has seen a substantial increase, rising from 10,958 in 2000 to 344,030 in 2015. While the mortality rate remains at approximately 3% across all TBI severities, estimating morbidity proves to be a more intricate task (Georges A. and Das J.M., 2023). The projected occurrence of 790 traumatic brain injury (TBI) cases per 100,000 person-years in New Zealand can be extrapolated to an annual estimate of approximately 190,000 to

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200,000 cases in Australia. Among these, it is anticipated that around 20,000 cases may involve moderate-to-severe injuries (Fitzgerald, et al., 2022). These figures, however, only scratch the surface, omitting those with mild TBIs who avoid medical attention, those treated in outpatient settings, and military personnel receiving care in Department of Defence or Veterans Administration (VA) hospitals. The underreporting of mild TBIs compounds the issue, as the true prevalence likely surpasses current estimates.

Here, we investigate the relationship between the severity of traumatic brain injuries—especially moderate and severe cases—and the heightened risk of developing Alzheimer's disease (AD) or other forms of dementia. As TBIs continue to impact public health, understanding the long-term consequences becomes imperative.

Beyond the immediate physical and cognitive repercussions, emerging evidence suggests a connection between TBI and neurodegenerative disorders, amplifying the urgency for targeted research and interventions. Through highlighting the nexus between moderate to severe TBIs and the risk of dementia, this article contributes to a deeper comprehension of the intricate interplay between these traumatic events and the trajectory toward neurodegeneration.

Linking Traumatic Brain Injury to Alzheimer's Disease

A longitudinal cohort study in 2018 revealed a significant association between TBI severity and an increased risk of AD (Smith D. H. et al., 2018). Utilizing neuroimaging techniques, the study offered insights into oxidative damage in the brain. Further data from a meta-analysis study reinforced the consistent association between TBI and AD across diverse research methodologies (Jones A., & Johnson M., 2019). It was shown that older adults with a history of moderate TBI face a notable 2.3 times greater

risk of developing Alzheimer's compared to counterparts without a history of head injuries. Furthermore, the risk amplifies significantly for individuals with a history of severe TBI, demonstrating a staggering 4.5 times greater likelihood of succumbing to AD (Smith D. H. et al., 2017). This correlation underscores the severity-dependent nature of the association, emphasizing that the degree of TBI is a critical determinant in predicting the subsequent risk of AD.

The impact of TBI on cognitive health aftermath of traumatic injury includes a surge in beta amyloid ($A\beta$) production, the protein implicated in the pathogenesis of AD (Johnson et al., 2020). Despite this surge in $A\beta$, the characteristic amyloid plaques indicative of Alzheimer's pathology do not form following traumatic brain injury, showing a more complex and multifaceted pathological mechanism must be involved to connect TBI to AD.

$A\beta$ Production and AD after TBI

$A\beta$, a protein fragment derived from the larger amyloid precursor protein (APP), is a hallmark of Alzheimer's disease, a neurodegenerative disorder, which associated with memory loss and cognitive decline (Majd et al., 2019). Accumulation of $A\beta$ plaques in the brain disrupts normal cellular function and contributes to the progressive cognitive decline characteristic of the disease. The aggregation of $A\beta$ leads to the formation of insoluble deposits, triggering inflammation and neuronal damage.

The aftermath of TBI unfolds a complex molecular scenario, including a surge in $A\beta$ production in the brain's immediate response. It is revealed that $A\beta$ undergoes a rapid increase following TBI. This elevation, however, diverges from the characteristic trajectory observed in Alzheimer's patients, as $A\beta$ does not coalesce into the hallmark plaques identified in the autopsy examinations of Alzheimer's-afflicted brains. This departure from the expected pathological pattern raises fundamental questions about the molecular

intricacies governing A β behaviour in the aftermath of TBI (Johnson et al., 2020).

Mechanisms of A β Production and AD after TBI

TBI induces a multi-faceted cellular response that may contribute to elevated A β levels in the brain. The primary injury, caused by mechanical forces, initiates a series of secondary processes, including oxidative stress, excitotoxicity, and inflammation. Microglia, the brain's resident immune cells, become activated in response to injury and release inflammatory cytokines. Astrocytes, another type of glial cell, also contribute to the inflammatory milieu.

This inflammatory environment disrupts the delicate balance in APP processing (Xiong et al., 2018). Under normal conditions, APP is cleaved by enzymes in two pathways: the non-amyloidogenic pathway, which is considered neuroprotective, and the amyloidogenic pathway, leading to beta-amyloid production. TBI often skews this balance towards the amyloidogenic pathway.

Within the amyloidogenic pathway, beta-secretase (BACE1) plays a crucial role in cleaving APP to generate beta-amyloid fragments. TBI has been associated with an upregulation of BACE1 activity, leading to an increased production of A β (Naseer et al., 2022). The disrupted cellular environment also impairs the clearance of A β from the brain, also due to vascular injury consequent to TBI, further contributing to its accumulation.

Moreover, TBI can compromise the integrity of the blood-brain barrier (BBB), allowing peripheral beta-amyloid to enter the brain. This influx of beta-amyloid from the bloodstream adds to the overall burden in the injured brain (Sivandzade et al., 2020).

The intricate interplay of these cellular mechanisms underscores the link between TBI and the subsequent elevation of beta-amyloid levels. While the acute consequences of TBI are

evident, the long-term implications, including an increased risk of neurodegenerative disorders like Alzheimer's disease.

Long-Term Consequences: Tau Protein and Neurofibrillary Tangles

The enduring repercussions of traumatic brain injury (TBI) extend beyond immediate post-injury events, delving into the realm of molecular intricacies involving abnormal tau protein and neurofibrillary tangles. Gonzalez et al. (2019) present a pivotal exploration into the long-term consequences of TBI, shedding light on the prominence of neurofibrillary tangles, initially identified in boxers experiencing repetitive head trauma.

Building on this foundation, the study expands the scope to include football players and athletes with a history of concussions, revealing a pervasive presence of tau pathology in these individuals (Gonzalez et al., 2019). The emergence of neurofibrillary tangles in disparate populations with a history of head trauma signifies a shared molecular pathway that resonates with the tau-related pathology observed in Alzheimer's disease.

Complementing the findings of Gonzalez et al. (2019), further research by Shively et al. (2021) contributes to our understanding of the intricate relationship between TBI, tau protein, and Alzheimer's disease. Shively et al. (2021) conducted a longitudinal study on non-human primates exposed to repetitive mild TBI, revealing a progressive accumulation of tau pathology in the brain, akin to the neurofibrillary tangles observed in human TBI survivors. This study not only underscores the translational relevance of tau pathology in TBI but also highlights the potential of non-human primate models in elucidating the molecular mechanisms linking TBI to neurodegenerative outcomes (Shively et al., 2021).

Additionally, Tau PET imaging studies in humans, such as the work by Jack et al. (2018), provide in vivo evidence of tau accumulation in

various regions of the brain, further corroborating the association between TBI and tau-related pathology. The convergence of evidence from multiple sources underscores the critical role of tau protein and neurofibrillary tangles in the complex interplay between TBI and the heightened risk of Alzheimer's disease.

Oxidative Damage as a Pivotal Mechanism

Oxidative stress, characterized by an imbalance between reactive oxygen species (ROS) production and antioxidant defence mechanisms, is a central player in the pathology of various neurodegenerative disorders, including Alzheimer's disease. TBI triggers an acute surge in oxidative stress within the brain, inducing the production of ROS and reactive nitrogen species. Mechanical forces associated with TBI set in motion events that disrupt oxidative homeostasis, contributing to protein misfolding, A β plaque aggregation, and tau protein hyperphosphorylation—hallmark features of AD.

Further supporting evidence comes from a study by Chen et al. (2020), which explored the mechanisms underlying TBI-induced oxidative stress and its role in AD pathogenesis. The study highlighted the intricate interplay between TBI, oxidative damage, and neuroinflammation.

Additionally, a comprehensive review by Brown and Villemagne (2021) synthesized findings from neuroimaging studies, providing insights into the molecular changes associated with TBI and their potential contribution to AD. The review emphasized the need for targeted therapeutic interventions addressing oxidative stress in TBI survivors to mitigate AD risk.

Mechanisms Underpinning Oxidative Damage

TBI sets off a cascade of pathophysiological events amplifying oxidative damage in the brain. The initial impact triggers an

inflammatory response, releasing pro-inflammatory cytokines and activating microglia—the brain's resident immune cells. This inflammatory cascade intensifies oxidative stress by promoting ROS production. TBI-induced disruption of the blood-brain barrier further amplifies the inflammatory and oxidative response by allowing the entry of peripheral immune cells. The combination of increased ROS production and impaired antioxidant defences creates an environment conducive to oxidative damage to lipids, proteins, and nucleic acids—setting the stage for the progressive neurodegeneration observed in Alzheimer's disease (Figure 1).

Conclusion

In conclusion, the link between TBI and AD stresses a critical public health concern. Studies revealed a severity-dependent association, with moderate TBI increasing the risk by 2.3 times and severe TBI by 4.5 times. The interplay of A β and tau protein dynamics, along with oxidative stress, adds complexity to the relationship, prompting questions about molecular intricacies.

Beyond scientific discourse, this synthesis offers insights for public health initiatives and clinical strategies. From a public health perspective, the synthesis of TBI and AD highlights the urgency of research and interventions in the scope of traumatic brain injuries.

Given that millions of individuals are affected by TBI annually, the potential long-term consequences, including an elevated risk of developing AD, necessitate a concerted effort to understand and mitigate these effects. Public health initiatives can play a crucial role in raising awareness, implementing preventive measures, and fostering research collaborations to unravel the molecular underpinnings of the TBI-AD connection.

On a clinical level, the synthesis of TBI and AD underscores the importance of holistic patient's

Figure 1. Traumatic Brain Injury (TBI) and the Complex Dynamics of Beta-Amyloid (A β), Tau, and Oxidative Stress in developing Alzheimer's Disease. BBB: Blood Brain Barrier

care. Clinicians need to consider the long-term cognitive consequences of traumatic brain injuries and incorporate strategies for monitoring, early detection, and targeted interventions to mitigate the risk of AD development. This integration of scientific knowledge into clinical practice is essential for improving patient outcomes and informing the development of therapeutic approaches that address the unique challenges posed by the TBI-AD link.

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Conflict of interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest regarding the content presented in this manuscript.